

Data Mining Techniques To Facilitate The Integration Of Data In Data Warehouse

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Abstract—Data Warehouses and Data Mining techniques are becoming indispensable parts of business intelligence programs. Often Data Mining is used together with OLAP for data analysis. Basically, there are three things you can do with a data warehouse – classical BI, “operational” BI, and data mining. Data warehousing embraces technology of integrating data from multiple distributed data sources and using that data in annotated and aggregated form to support business decision-making and enterprise management. Although many techniques have been revisited or newly developed in the context of data warehouses, such as view maintenance and OLAP, little attention has been paid to data mining techniques for supporting the most important and costly tasks of data integration for data warehouse design.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. What is a data warehousing ?

1.The data warehouse is an informational environment that

- Provides an integrated and total view of the enterprise
- Makes the enterprise’s current and historical information easily available for decision making
- Makes decision-support transactions possible without hindering operational systems
- Renders the organization’s information consistent
- Presents a flexible and interactive source of strategic information

Data warehousing is really a simple concept: Take all the data you already have in the organization, clean and transform it and then provide useful strategic information.

2.An Environment, Not a Product

A data warehouse is not a single software or hardware product you purchase to provide strategic information. It is, rather, a computing environment where users can find strategic information, an environment where users are put directly in touch with the data they need to make better decisions. It is a user-centric environment [5].

Although a simple concept, it involves different functions: data extraction, the function of loading the data, transforming the data, storing the data, and providing user interfaces.[5]

A data warehouse is a “subject-oriented, integrated, time varying, non-volatile collection of data that is used primarily in organizational decision making.”[5] Typically, the data warehouse is maintained separately from the organization’s operational databases. There These tasks are structured and repetitive, and consist of short, atomic, isolated transactions. The transactions require detailed, up-to-date data, and read or update a few (tens of) records accessed typically on their

primary keys. Operational databases tend to be hundreds of megabytes to gigabytes in size. Consistency and recoverability of the database are critical, and maximizing transaction throughput is the key performance metric. Consequently, the database is designed to reflect the operational semantics of known applications, and, in particular, to minimize concurrency conflicts. Data warehouses, in contrast, are targeted for decision support. Historical, summarized and consolidated data is more important than detailed, individual records. Since data warehouses contain consolidated data, perhaps from several operational databases, over potentially long periods of time, they tend to be orders of magnitude larger than operational databases; enterprise data warehouses are projected to be hundreds of gigabytes to terabytes in size.

Data warehouses might be implemented on standard or extended relational DBMSs, called Relational OLAP (ROLAP) servers. These servers assume that data is stored in relational databases, and they support extensions to SQL and special access and implementation methods to efficiently implement the multidimensional data model and operations. In contrast, multidimensional OLAP (MOLAP) servers are servers that directly store multidimensional data in special data structures (e.g., arrays) and implement the OLAP operations over these special data structures. There is more to building and maintaining a data warehouse than selecting an OLAP server and defining a schema and some complex queries for the warehouse. Different architectural alternatives exist. Many organizations want to implement an integrated enterprise warehouse that collects information about all subjects (e.g., customers, products, sales, assets, personnel) spanning the whole organization. However, building an enterprise warehouse is a long and complex process, requiring extensive business modeling, and may take many years to succeed. Some organizations are settling for *data marts* instead, which are departmental subsets focused on selected subjects (e.g., a marketing data mart may include customer, product, and sales information). These data marts enable faster roll out, since they do not require enterprise-wide consensus, but they may lead to complex integration problems in the long run, if a complete business model is not developed.[5]

B. Architecture Of Data Warehousing

Figure 1 shows a typical data warehousing architecture.

Figure 1. Data Warehousing Architecture

An ETL process which includes extraction ,transformation and loading .It includes tools for extracting data from multiple operational databases and external sources; for cleaning, transforming and integrating this data; for loading data into the data warehouse; and for periodically refreshing the warehouse to reflect updates at the sources and to purge data from the warehouse, perhaps onto slower archival storage. In addition to the main warehouse, there may be several departmental data marts. Data in the warehouse and data marts is stored and managed by one or more warehouse servers, which present multidimensional views of data to a variety of front end tools: query tools, report writers, analysis tools, and data mining tools. Finally, there is a repository for storing and managing metadata, and tools for monitoring and administering the warehousing system..[6]

Figure 2 :Typical data source environment.

The real challenge of ETL functions is the pulling together of all the source data from many disparate, dissimilar source systems. As of today, most the data warehouses get data extracted from a combination of legacy mainframe systems, old minicomputer applications, and some newer client/server systems. Most of these source systems do not conform to the same set of business rules. Very often they follow different naming conventions and varied standards for data representation. Figure 2 shows a typical data source environment. Notice the challenging issues indicated in the

figure Integrating the data is the combining of all the relevant operational data into coherent data structures to be made ready for loading into the data warehouse. You may want to think of data integration and consolidation as a type of preprocess before other major transformation routines are applied. You have to standardize the names and data representations and resolve discrepancies in the ways in which same data is represented in different source systems. Although time-consuming, many of the data integration tasks can be managed. However, let us go over a couple of more difficult challenges.

1.Entity Identification Problem. If you have three different legacy applications developed in your organization at different times in the past, you are likely to have three different customer files supporting those systems. One system may be the old order entry system, another the customer service support system, and the third the marketing system .Most of the customers will be common to all three files. The same customer on each of the files may have a unique identification number. These unique identification numbers for the same customer may not be the same across the three systems .This is a problem of identification in which you do not know which of the customer records relate to the same customer. But in the data warehouse you need to keep a single record for each customer. You must be able to get the activities of the single customer from the various source systems and then match up with the single record to be loaded to the data warehouse. This is a common but very difficult problem in many enterprises where applications have evolved over time from the distant past. This type of problem is prevalent where multiple sources exist for the same entities. Vendors, suppliers, employees, and sometimes products are the kinds of entities that are prone to this type of problem .In the above example of the three customer files, you have to design complex algorithms to match records from all the three files and form groups of matching records.

2.Multiple Sources Problem. This is another kind of problem affecting data integration ,although less common and less complex than the entity identification problem. This problem results from a single data element having more than one source. For example, suppose unit cost of products is available from two systems. In the standard costing application, cost values are calculated and updated at specific intervals. Your order processing system also carries the unit costs for all products. There could be slight variations in the cost figures from these two systems. From which system should you get the cost for storing in the data warehouse? A straightforward solution is to assign a higher priority to one of the two sources and pick up the product unit cost from that source. Sometimes, a straightforward solution such as this may not sit well with needs of the data warehouse users. 3.Transformation for Dimension Attributes :The ways to handle the three types of slowly changing dimensions. Type 1 changes are corrections of errors. These changes are applied to the data warehouse without any need to preserve history. Type 2 changes preserve

the history in the data warehouse. Type 3 changes are tentative changes where your users need the ability to analyze the metrics in both ways—with the changes and without the changes. In order to apply the changes correctly, you need to transform the incoming changes and prepare the changes to the data for loading into the data warehouse. Figure 2 illustrates how the data extraction of the changes in the source systems are transformed and prepared for data loading. This figure shows the handling of each type of changes to dimension tables. Types 1, 2, and 3 are shown distinctly. Please review the figure carefully to get a good grasp of the solutions. You will be faced with dimension table changes all the time.[5]

C. Data Mining

Data mining can be viewed as a result of the natural evolution of information technology. Data mining refers to extracting or “mining” knowledge from large amounts of data. Many other terms carry a similar or slightly different meaning to data mining, such as knowledge mining from data, knowledge extraction, data/pattern analysis, data archaeology, and data dredging. Many people treat data mining as a synonym for another popularly used term, Knowledge Discovery from Data, or KDD. Alternatively, others view data mining as simply an essential step in the process of knowledge discovery.

The article is organized as the second section gives details of data mining techniques used for data integration at data warehouse.

II. DATA MINING TECHNIQUES FOR DATA INTEGRATION

Using data mining techniques to facilitate the integration of data in Data Warehouse.

A Data integration

The integration is one of the most important characteristic of the data warehouse. Data is fed from multiple disparate sources into the data warehouse. As the data is fed it is converted, reformatted, summarized, and so forth. The result is that data—once it resides in the data warehouse—has a single physical corporate image.

Many problems arise in this process. Designers of different applications made up their decisions over the years in different ways. In the past, when application designers built an application, they never considered that the data they were operating on would ever have to be integrated with other data. Such a consideration was only a wild theory. Consequently, across multiple applications there is no application consistency in encoding, naming conventions, physical attributes, measurement of attributes, and so forth. Each application designer has had free rein to make his or her own design decisions. The result is that any application is very different from any other application. One simple example of lack of integration is data that is not encoded consistently, as shown by the encoding of gender. In one application, gender is encoded as m or f. In another, it is encoded as 0 or 1. As data passes to the data warehouse, the applications’ different values must be correctly deciphered and recoded with the

proper value. This consideration of consistency applies to all application design issues, such as naming conventions, key structure, measurement of attributes, and physical characteristics of data. Some of the same data exists in various places with different names, some data is labeled the same way in different places, some data is all in the same place with the same name but reflects a different measurement, and so on. Whatever integration architecture we choose, there are different problems that come up when trying to integrate data from various sources. [1]

B. Schema Integration

The most important issue in data integration is the Schema integration. How can equivalent real-world entities from multiple data sources be matched up? This is referred to as entity identification process. Terms may be given different interpretations at different sources. For example, how can be data analyst be sure that customer_id in one database and cust_number in another refer the same entity? Data mining algorithms can be used to discover the implicit information about the semantics of the data structures of the information sources. Often, the exact meaning of an attribute cannot be deduced from its name and data type. The task of reconstructing the meaning of attributes would be optimally supported by dependency modeling using data mining techniques and mapping this model against expert knowledge, e.g., business models. Association rules are suited for this purpose. Other data mining techniques, e.g., classification tree and rule induction, and statistical methods, e.g., multivariate regression, probabilistic networks, can also produce useful hypotheses in this context. Many attribute values are (numerically) encoded. Identifying inter-field dependencies helps to build hypotheses about encoding schemes when the semantics of some fields are known. Also encoding schemes change over. Data mining algorithms are useful to identify changes in encoding schemes, the time when they took place, and the part of the code that is effected. Methods which use data sets to train a “normal” behavior can be adapted to the task. The model learned can be used to evaluate significant changes. A further approach would be to partition the data set, to build models on these partitions applying the same data mining algorithms, and to compare the differences between these models Data mining and statistical methods can be used to induce integrity constraint candidates from the data. These include, for example, visualization methods to identify distributions for finding domains of attributes or methods for dependency modeling. Other data mining methods can find intervals of attribute values, which are rather compact and cover a high percentage of the existing values. Once each single data source is understood, content and structural integration follows. This step involves resolving different kinds of structural and semantic conflicts. To a certain degree, data mining methods can be used to identify and resolve these conflicts. Data mining methods can discover functional relationships between different databases when they are not too complex. A linear regression method would discover the

corresponding conversion factors. If the type of functional dependency (linear, quadratic, exponential etc.) is a priori not known, model search instead of parameter search has to be applied.[2]

C. Redundancy

Redundancy is another important issue. An attribute may be redundant if it can be “derived” from another table, e.g. annual revenue. In addition to detecting redundancies between attributes, duplication can be detected at the tuple level (e.g., where there are two or more identical tuples for a given unique data entry case). Some redundancies can be detected by correlation analysis. For example, given two attributes, such analysis can measure how strongly one attribute implies the other, based on available data. Inconsistencies in attribute or dimension naming can also cause redundancies in the resulting data set.

D. Inconsistencies

Since a data warehouse is used for decision-making, it is important that the data in the warehouse are correct. However, since large volumes of data from multiple sources are involved, there is a high probability of errors and anomalies in the data. Real-world data tend to be incomplete, noisy and inconsistent. Data cleansing is a non-trivial task in data warehouse environments. The main focus is the identification of missing or incorrect data (noise) and conflicts between data of different sources and the correction of these problems. Data cleansing routines attempt to fill in missing values, smooth out noise while identifying outliers, and correct inconsistencies in the data. Some examples where data cleaning becomes necessary are: inconsistent field lengths, inconsistent descriptions, inconsistent value assignments, missing entries and violation of integrity constraints. Typically, missing values are indicated by blank fields or special attribute values. A way to handle these records is to replace them by the mean of most frequent value or the value, which is most common to similar objects. Simple transformation rules can be specified; e.g., “replace the string gender by sex”. Missing values may be determined with regression, inference-based tools, using a Bayesian formalism, or decision tree induction. Advanced data mining methods for completion could be similarity based methods or methods for dependency modeling to get hypotheses for missing values. On the other hand, data entries might be wrong or noisy. For such kind of problems is proper to be used tree or rule induction methods. If we have a model that describe dependencies between data, every transaction that deviate from the model is a hint for an error or noise.

There are some Data scrubbing tools that use domain-specific knowledge (e.g., postal addresses) to do the scrubbing of data. They often exploit parsing and fuzzy matching techniques to accomplish cleaning from multiple sources. Some tools make it possible to specify the “relative cleanliness” of sources. Another tools -Data auditing tools make it possible to discover rules and relationships (or to signal violation of stated rules) by scanning data. Thus, such tools may be considered as variants of data mining tools. For example, such a tool may

discover a suspicious pattern (based on statistical analysis) that a certain car dealer has never received any complaints. Different sources can contain ambiguous or inconsistent data, e.g., different values for the address of a customer or the price of the same article. With clustering methods you might find records, which describe the same real-world entity but differ in some attributes, which have to be cleaned. Record linkage techniques are used to link together records, which relate to the same entity (e.g. patient or customer) in one or more data sets where a unique identifier is not available.

E. Multidimensional Data Modeling

Data sets for analysis may contain hundreds of attributes, many of which may be irrelevant or redundant. Sometimes it is not sensible to model all the fields as dimensions of the cube as some fields are functionally dependent and other fields do not strongly influence the measures. Although it may be possible for domain expert to pick out some of the useful attributes, this can be a difficult time-consuming task, especially when the behavior of data is not well known. Data mining methods can help to rank the variables according to their importance in the domain. Non-correlated sets of attributes can be found with correlation analysis. Furthermore, using data mining methods to drive this cube design seems promising as they can help to identify (possibly weak) functional dependencies, which indicate non-orthogonal dimension attributes. Sparse regions should be avoided during modeling. Using special cluster methods (e.g. probability density estimation) data points can be identified as the center of dense regions. The multidimensional paradigm demands that dimensions are of discrete data type. Therefore, attributes with a continuous domain have to be mapped to discrete values if this attribute is to be modeled as a dimension. Algorithms, that find meaningful intervals in numeric attributes help to get discrete values.

CONCLUSION

The article presents the idea of using data mining methods for supporting the most important and costly tasks of data warehousing – data integration.

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